

Application of Reinforcement Learning to Multigroup Energy Grid Optimization for Criticality Problems

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ABSTRACT

The development of optimal multigroup energy grid structures is an important research topic in neutron transport. This work presents a novel approach for optimizing energy grids using a reinforcement learning framework based on the Proximal Policy Optimization algorithm with action masking, guided by a convolutional neural network (CNN) surrogate model. The reinforcement learning model begins with a large number of energy groups and iteratively removes energy bounds until a target energy grid structure is created. The reward function incorporates the performance of the new energy group structure with the total number of energy groups. The surrogate model is designed to classify the deviation of a candidate configuration's k_{eff} from a reference value, rather than to predict the absolute k_{eff} itself. This formulation enables the model to estimate the accuracy of proposed energy group structures without the need to repeatedly run computationally expensive transport simulations. The trained reinforcement learning models create group structures that outperform commonly used group structures for both subcritical Godiva and BeRP ball examples. These models also achieve accuracy comparable to hierarchical agglomeration while requiring significantly less computational cost. Future work includes expanding on the surrogate model to include problem specific information, such as material composition and spatial distributions, to improve generalization across different systems. Additional directions include developing agents capable of both adding and deleting energy bounds, as well as extending the framework to use continuous energy representations instead of high fidelity energy grids as the initial grid for optimization.

Keywords: Reinforcement Learning, Machine Learning, Nuclear Data, Multigroup, Energy Grid Optimization

1. INTRODUCTION

The neutron transport equation models the movement of neutrons through materials. Due to the high dimensionality of this equation, the solution is approximated through deterministic and probabilistic methods [1]. Various discretization schemes have been developed to handle the equation's seven dimensions (3 spatial, 2 angular, energy, and time) to make the numerical solutions tractable. One such method, the multigroup method, integrates the energy variable over finite ranges, referred to as energy groups. Careful selection of the integration limits, or energy group bounds, is crucial as suboptimal energy grid structures can lead to suboptimal neutron flux approximations.

Widely used energy group structures, such as the LANL618 energy grid [2], are common in the neutron transport industry but continue to be refined, making energy group optimization an active field of research (e.g. [3, 4]). This work presents a novel technique that utilizes reinforcement learning (RL) for energy grid optimization. RL agents are trained using neural network surrogate models to remove energy group bounds from the LANL618 grid to find an optimal target group structure. This has been shown to be effective for subcritical Godiva and Beryllium Reflected Plutonium (BeRP) ball problems

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and requires less computational load than previously used optimization techniques [3]. Transport simulations were performed using PARTISN [5] on fast critical systems to minimize the impact of the resonance range.

The organization of this paper is as follows. Section 2 introduces the k -eigenvalue neutron transport equation, multigroup cross sections, and the energy grid formulation. Section 3 presents the RL algorithm used and how the neural network surrogate models were constructed for decreased training times. Section 4 shows RL results and Section 5 presents the conclusions and areas of future work.

2. THE NEUTRON TRANSPORT EQUATION

The time-independent angular flux $\Psi(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, E)$ depends on a spatial coordinate $\mathbf{x} \in D \subset \mathbb{R}^3$, angular coordinate $\boldsymbol{\Omega} \in \mathbb{S}^2$, and energy $E > 0$ while the scalar flux $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, E)$ integrates the angular flux over the angular dimension. The continuous k -eigenvalue criticality transport equation

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \Psi(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, E) + \sigma^t(\mathbf{x}, E) \Psi(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, E) = \int_0^\infty dE' \sigma^s(\mathbf{x}, E' \rightarrow E) \Phi(\mathbf{x}, E') + \frac{\chi(\mathbf{x}, E)}{k_{\text{eff}}} \int_0^\infty dE' \nu(x, E') \sigma^f(\mathbf{x}, E') \Phi(\mathbf{x}, E') \quad (1)$$

estimates the generational change in neutron population. σ^t , σ^s , and σ^f are the total, scattering, and fission cross sections respectively; ν is the average number of neutrons created from a fission event; χ is the probability of the resulting neutron energy; and k_{eff} is the effective multiplication factor.

2.1. Multigroup Cross Sections

The multigroup method discretizes neutron cross sections in energy by approximating them as piecewise constants in energy “bins.” The energy group is represented with $g \in \mathcal{G} := \{1, \dots, G\}$, where $0 = E_0 < E_1 < \dots < E_g < E_{g+1} < \dots < E_G = E_{\text{max}}$ are the energy bounds with $E_{\text{max}} = 20$ MeV in this work. The groupwise total cross section value is an approximate weighted average of its continuum counterpart,

$$\sigma_g^t(x) \approx \left[\int_{E_{g-1}}^{E_g} dE \sigma^t(\mathbf{x}, E) \Phi(\mathbf{x}, E) \right] / \left[\int_{E_{g-1}}^{E_g} dE \Phi(\mathbf{x}, E) \right]. \quad (2)$$

Since $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, E)$ is not known a priori, the averaging process relies on assumed spectral and angular shape of the solution, typically prescribed within nuclear data processing software such as NJOY [6].

2.2. Energy Grid Formulation

The choice of the energy group bounds, $E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{G-1}, E_G$, strongly influences the accuracy of the neutron flux approximation. Identifying the optimal group structures is difficult as it is dependent on problem specific factors such as material composition, geometry, and orientation. These difficulties are further exacerbated by experimental errors and nuclear data uncertainties, resonance behavior, and the need for appropriate flux weighting factor as in Eq. (2). Higher number of energy groups often equates to a more accurate flux approximation, albeit with longer computational times and a larger memory footprint. On the other hand, fewer groups can alleviate memory and computational constraints but place higher emphasis on selecting energy bound locations. The relationship between energy groups and accuracy is not strictly monotonic, as discretization and modeling errors can sometimes partially offset one another. Therefore, an optimal balance must be found between benefiting from such error cancellation and minimizing underlying modeling inaccuracies.

Energy grids, such as LANL30 and LANL618 [2], are widely used for multigroup neutron transport simulations, and yet their refinement remains an active area of research. One approach to improving

these standard grids is the hierarchical agglomeration method [3], a greedy algorithm that starts by initializing a G energy grid structure and iteratively removing one boundary at each step until a $G - M$ group structure is reached after M iterations. In the first iteration, $G + 1$ transport simulations are performed to evaluate the effect of each boundary, and the boundary whose removal has the least impact on solution accuracy is selected. In subsequent iterations, the number of candidate boundaries decreases by one each time as the grid coarsens. Although effective, this method has the possibility to converge to local minima and can become computationally expensive if $G - M$ or G is large.

3. REINFORCEMENT LEARNING FOR ENERGY GRID OPTIMIZATION

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is a subset of machine learning that focuses on mapping states to actions [7]. RL models actively learn from their environment instead of using datasets for regression or identifying underlying structures. Given a state s_t , an agent takes an action a_t and receives a reward r_t based on that action and state. The agent observes the updated state s_{t+1} to take the next action a_{t+1} , repeating the process for T steps in an episode. The agent's actions or policy $\pi(a|s)$ determines which action to take given the current state, with the intent of maximizing the reward by finding the optimal policy π^* .

3.1. Proximal Policy Optimization

The Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) is one of many algorithms used to calculate the optimal policy [8]. PPO is part of the policy gradient methods that maximizes a surrogate objective function

$$L^{\text{CLIP}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E} [\min (r_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) \hat{A}_t)] \quad (3)$$

to update the policy's parameters θ with a constraint to allow for stable learning. In Eq. (3), $r_t(\theta)$ is the probability ratio between the new and old policies and \hat{A}_t is the advantage function estimator, which approximates the advantage of one action over others. The clip function limits the magnitude of policy updates, with $\epsilon \in [0, 1]$ defining the clip range. The Stable-Baselines3 [9] implementation of the PPO algorithm was used to train RL agents for energy grid optimization.

3.2. Formulation of the Group Structure Optimization Problem

The approach for group structure optimization via hierarchical agglomeration can be reformulated to be used with RL. Instead of running simulations for every $G - 1$ energy group structure variation, an RL model learns to remove energy bounds based on their usefulness to the specific simulation. LANL618 grid is chosen as the reference structure, from which all new formulated groups are derived as subsets. The RL model will have 619 possible discrete actions, one for each energy group bound, with a multi-binary observation space of length 619. To limit the actions of the policy to strictly removing energy group bounds, action-masking is used to set the probability of selecting invalid actions to zero [10].

Each episode is initialized by sampling from a probability density function derived from common subsets of LANL618. At each step, the agent takes an appropriate action and is given a reward based on the performance of the resulting energy group. This process is repeated for T iterations until an optimal target group structure is obtained. A detailed description of the reward function is discussed in Section 3.4.

3.3. Acceleration of Reinforcement Learning Training

A key challenge in training the RL model is that each time a new energy group structure is generated, a transport simulation must be performed, requiring millions of simulations across all steps and episodes. To address this, a surrogate model is introduced that reduces the required number of simulations to train an RL model by over 95%. This surrogate model employs convolutional neural networks (CNNs) that take the proposed energy grid structure as input and predicts its accuracy ranking. The input is a

binary vector of size 619, where ones indicate the presence of energy boundaries. The output is a 10-class classification representing the predicted accuracy, with higher classification values corresponding to more accurate group structures. Because this prediction represents an ordered ranking rather than independent categories, a rank-based classification approach was used, implementing a cost-sensitive loss function with different cost matrices.

The metric used to determine the accuracy of new group structures is $\Delta k_{\text{eff}} = |k_{\text{eff}}^* - k_{\text{eff}}|$ where k_{eff}^* is the reference k_{eff} value using the full LANL618 group structure. Additional metrics to incorporate scalar flux errors and reaction rate errors such as the metric in [4] are also being investigated.

3.4. The Reward Function

A critical part of RL is the creation of the reward function, which determines the reward the RL agent will receive given the current state s_t , and “teaches” the agent to take desirable actions. Given the constraints on the RL agent, the reward function is only dependent on the performance of the proposed energy grid. Additional terms, such as the number of energy groups and number of steps for each state, will be investigated when expanding the RL capabilities however they are not necessary with the current RL setup. The reward function r is represented as

$$r(s_t) = \begin{cases} r_{\text{success}} & G = G_{\text{min}}, \arg \max p(s_t) = N \\ 2(y_{\text{class}} - 1)/(N - 1) - 1 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4a)$$

$$y_{\text{class}} = \sum_{n=1}^N p(s_t)_n n \quad (4b)$$

which takes in the current state s_t following the energy bound removal in action a_{t-1} . The state s_t is a binary vector of length 619 where the number of energy groups is represented as $G = (\sum s_t) - 1$. Each episode ends when the state reaches the target number of energy groups $G = G_{\text{min}}$. If the surrogate model classifies the state at $G = G_{\text{min}}$ with the highest performance bin, an additional reward, $r_{\text{success}} = 100$ is given, otherwise, a normalized reward between $[-1, 1]$ is applied based on the surrogate model classification prediction. The multiclass classification surrogate model uses 10 classes, $N = 10$, where the first bin ($n = 1$) indicates the worst performing energy group structure and the last bin ($n = N = 10$) indicates the best. The output of the surrogate model is represented as y_{class} , which takes the probability of each classification $p(s_t)$ and multiplies it by the class number to account for uncertainties in the model.

4. RESULTS

This section presents the results of applying the RL-based energy grid optimization to two one-dimensional spherical systems. The first example is a subcritical Godiva configuration ($k_{\text{eff}} \approx 0.928$), representing an unreflected uranium system composed of a mixture of ^{234}U , ^{235}U , and ^{238}U . The second example is a subcritical BeRP ball ($k_{\text{eff}} \approx 0.922$), consisting of an inner sphere of plutonium surrounded by an outer shell of beryllium. In both of these examples, the material composition, spatial mesh, and discrete ordinates are held constant, varying only the energy group structure.

For each problem, a surrogate model is used to drastically reduce the RL training time by approximating the performance of each proposed energy group structure instead of running full transport simulations. The surrogate model is coupled with the RL reward function in Eq. (4a) to find an optimal final group structure. Two RL models were trained for each example problem, one targeting a 30 group grid and another targeting a 70 group grid, noted as RL30 and RL70, respectively. The default parameters from Stable-Baselines3 were used except for the learning rate which was set at 7.5×10^{-5} . Training began from randomly initialized group structures containing $G \in [30, 600]$ energy groups or $G \in [70, 600]$ energy groups, respectively, allowing for flexibility in the starting energy grid.. At each step, the RL

model selects and removes one energy bound until reaching the target group structure. Each model was trained for five million steps, reducing training time from weeks to hours through the use of the surrogate model. The resulting RL-optimized group structures can then be compared to their commonly used group structure counterparts, LANL30 and LANL70, as well as those selected using the hierarchical agglomeration approach. LANL301 group structure was used as a common starting point for all approaches.

4.1. Godiva

The Godiva problem surrogate model was trained using 2,000 randomly generated group structures for energy groups $G \in [30, 99]$, using a 60/20/20 train/validation/test split. The neural network consists of four CNN layers (64, 64, 128, 128 filters), three fully connected hidden layers (2304, 288, 256 nodes), and dropout layers to prevent overfitting. The Adam optimizer, cross entropy loss, 80 epochs, 80 samples per batch, and a learning rate of 10^{-4} were used. The Δk_{eff} metric used 25, 45, 62, 80, 100, 125, 165, 210, and 300 pcm as the classification bin edges, which were chosen to keep a similar number of samples in each class. Testing data consisted of cases with 60,984 random group structures between $G \in [30, 618]$, and the resulting confusion matrix is shown in Fig. 1(a). This matrix compares predicted classification against the true classification for the surrogate model, with the diagonal elements representing correctly classified samples (true accuracy). The true accuracy was 93.943%, while including the tri-diagonal elements (adjacent accuracy), representing misclassifications to adjacent classes, yields 99.998% accuracy. The adjacent accuracy is included to show the accuracy of the misclassifications that are adjacent to the true class, seen in ordinal classification.

Figure 1. The confusion matrix for the Godiva and BeRP ball surrogate models on test data showing predicted vs. true classifications for random group structures. The adjacent accuracy is reported due to the ordinal relationship between the classes. (a) The Godiva problem was trained in the range $G \in [30, 99]$ and tested in the range $G \in [30, 618]$. (b) The BeRP ball was trained with samples $G \in [20, 50]$ and tested with $G \in [50, 618]$.

The RL models, initialized with LANL301 energy group generated optimal $G = 30$ and $G = 70$ energy

Figure 2. (a) Shows the true Δk_{eff} for the RL and hierarchical agglomeration models. The RL30 and RL70 models outperformed the commonly used LANL30 and LANL70 group structures. The RL models were limited by the classification bin sizes of the surrogate model. (b) Shows the total cross section for the final group structure for the RL model. The LANL30 group structure maintains energy bins in the thermal region while the RL model concentrates its group structure in the fast region.

grids, referred to as RL30 and RL70. For comparison, the hierarchical agglomeration was also applied using the same starting point to create an optimal $G = 30$ group structure. The results comparing the Δk_{eff} error metric for each step in the energy grid reduction process is shown in Fig. 2(a). Godiva problem results using the LANL30 and LANL70 group structures are also included. The performance of the RL30 and RL70 energy grids are evaluated at the final step given the formulation of the RL training, which show lower Δk_{eff} values than their associated LANL30 and LANL70 counterparts. The hierarchical agglomeration method achieved smaller errors than those of the RL-optimized group structures primarily due to limitations of the surrogate model: the final RL group structures fall within the highest performance classification bin (errors below 25 pcm), effectively imposing a 25 pcm tolerance on the optimization. Reducing the classification bin width in the surrogate model should improve resolution and yield more accurate RL group structures. Despite this limitation, the hierarchical agglomeration model required days to converge, while the RL30 and RL70 models completed training in approximately five hours on a laptop.

The energy group structure the RL model chose for the $G = 30$ structure is shown in Fig. 2(b) and compared to the LANL30 group structure. The RL-optimized group structure concentrates its boundaries in the fast energy region with no thermal bounds and a single bound through the resonance region, while the LANL30 structure provides finer resolution in the thermal and resonance regions. These choices by the RL model align with the characteristics of the Godiva system, in which the fast energy region dominates neutron behavior.

4.2. BeRP Ball

The surrogate model for the BeRP ball was trained using 10,000 random group structures for energy groups $G \in [20, 50]$ using a 60/20/20 train/validation/test split. This surrogate model consists of three CNN layers (32, 128, 256 filters), three fully connected hidden layers (1536, 1536, 288 nodes), and dropout layers to prevent overfitting. The Adam optimizer, cost sensitive loss, 40 epochs, 120 samples

per batch, and a learning rate of 10^{-4} were used. The Δk_{eff} metric was used with the classification bin edges of 73, 140, 200, 260, 320, 380, 460, 580, and 830 pcm to keep a similar number of samples in each classification bin. These bin sizes are larger than those in the Godiva problem, indicating higher error for suboptimal group structures. 19,976 random group structures with $G \in [50, 618]$ energy groups were used to test this model with the confusion matrix result shown in Fig. 1(b). Comparing the test result with the Godiva problem shows that there is a decrease in true accuracy on the diagonal (75.466% compared to 93.943%), although the adjacent accuracy is similar. This is likely due to the complexity of the BeRP ball system, where only using the energy group bounds with a convolutional neural network provides limited information for predicting energy group structure performance. Although the BeRP ball results demonstrate that the method is still applicable, incorporating spatial and material information may further improve predictive accuracy in future work.

Figure 3. Similar as in Fig. 2(a) and 2(b) for BeRP ball.

The results for the trained RL and hierarchical agglomeration models for both $G = 30$ and $G = 70$ group structures are shown in Fig. 3(a), comparing the true Δk_{eff} for the group structure at each energy group. The RL30 and RL70 models produced optimal energy grid structures while outperforming their LANL30 and LANL70 counterparts. Similar to Godiva results, the difference between the RL formed group structures Δk_{eff} value and that of hierarchical agglomeration can be attributed to the resolution of surrogate model prediction. Unlike hierarchical agglomeration, which takes several days to compute each configuration, the trained RL models can generate new optimized grids from different starting group without additional computational cost.

The comparison between the RL30 optimized group structure with the LANL30 group structure is shown using the plutonium cross section distribution in Fig. 3(b). The RL30 group structure added more energy groups in the fast region than LANL30, which indicates the emphasis on this being a fast system. One difference between the energy grids for Godiva and BeRP is that the BeRP RL30 includes finer thermal and resonance energy bins. The evolution of the number of thermal and resonance groups warrants further examination, particularly under changes in material orientation and composition.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces a novel method that applies CNN based surrogate model enabled reinforcement learning to optimize energy group structures of criticality problems. The RL models are able to start

from a high number of energy groups and remove bounds until they reach an optimal target group structure that outperforms widely used energy grids for one-dimensional Godiva and BeRP ball problems. In both problems, the RL model correctly identified the fast energy region as the most influential. The RL models were able to achieve results comparable to previously developed hierarchical agglomeration technique at a fraction of the computational cost.

Several topics for future research remain. The surrogate model could employ a more representative performance metric than Δk_{eff} to better capture differences between group structures. Incorporating additional information about the problem, such as material composition, spatial orientation, and the cross section data, would improve surrogate model generalization. The framework could also be extended to a multi-agent reinforcement learning formulation, where agents are capable of adding as well as removing group boundaries. Finally, while the current study constrained all grids to be a subset of the LANL618 group structure, future work may explore continuous energy formulations or increasing the RL agents' actions to allow for perturbing existing boundaries for finer optimization.

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